

SYNTHESIS AND VOLT-AMPERE CHARACTERIZATION OF AN ELECTRICALLY CONDUCTIVE COMPOSITE POLYMER BASED ON POLYVINYL IMIDAZOLE

S. Otajonov¹, J. Mamatov², Y.G. Zelenskiy³, D. Kuranboyev⁴, N. Kattaev⁵, Kh. Akbarov⁶

Department of Chemistry, National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan^{1,2,3,4,5,6}

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Abstract. Poly(1-N-vinylimidazole) (PVIm) was obtained by the radical polymerization of 1-N-vinylimidazole in a benzene solution in an inert environment at a temperature of 60 °C. Its hydrophilic derivative was synthesised by chemical modification of PVIm with 2-amino-5-bromo-1,3,4-tiadiazol. The structure of the synthesised polymers was studied by IR spectroscopy, Notably, absorption bands that were absent in the PVIm spectrum but appeared in the PVIm-Tia-NH₂ spectrum—at 1567.7 cm⁻¹ (N–H), 994.8 cm⁻¹ (C–N), as well as 647.8 cm⁻¹ and 621.12 cm⁻¹ (C–S)—confirm that the reaction took place and that PVIm was successfully converted into PVIm-Tia-NH₂. V-I characteristic, It was confirmed that electrical conductivity obeys Ohm's law in all samples. It is worth noting that in both cases (in the dark and when saturated with ultraviolet light), the current strength in PVim-tia-NH₂ comp ($I=\mu A$) increases by one unit compared to PVIm($I=nA$). The sharp increase in the result when saturated with ultraviolet light compared to the result obtained in the dark can be explained by the internal photoeffect phenomenon.

Keywords: 1-N-vinylimidazole, radical polymerization, synthesis, poly-(1-N-vinylimidazole), chemical modification, electrical conductivity, photoconductivity, V-I characteristic.

Introduction. Electrically conductive polymers attract great scientific and practical interest due to their potential applications in various fields of technology. Composite materials based on conductive polymers are lightweight and serve as durable conductive elements. They are also capable of absorbing electromagnetic radiation of different wavelengths. The electrochemical and ion-exchange properties of such materials make it possible to use them in accumulator electrodes, ion-exchange materials, and as ion-selective electrodes. The flexibility of conductive materials makes them promising for the development of sensors and similar devices. The most widely used representatives of this class of polymers include polypyrrole, polyaniline, polythiophene, poly(p-phenylene), and some of their derivatives [1–3].

Poly(N-vinylimidazole) (PVIm), which is soluble in a number of organic solvents, is considered a promising polymer since it contains an electron-rich aromatic ring with heteroatoms such as pyridine, pyrrole, thiophene, and others, and therefore can form charge transfer complexes. Thus, changes in the inductive charge of substituents should lead to a redistribution of electron density, i.e., to a modification of the electronic structure of the polymer. Polyvinylimidazole, which has a non-conjugated structure, was selected as a nitrogen-containing polymer matrix [4–7].

As a rule, single-component materials prepared from pure conductive polymers exhibit low mechanical strength and high brittleness, which significantly complicates their research and practical application. One of the approaches to solving this problem is the creation of composite systems consisting of an elastic substrate that provides mechanical properties and a conductive

polymer that serves as the active layer. Flexible-chain polymers such as polyethylene, polypropylene, polyvinylidene fluoride, and others are used as substrates. However, due to the low adhesion of the coating layer in these polymers, their application in composite systems is limited. An effective solution to this problem is the use of porous materials as substrates, since their large surface area enables good contact with the coating [5–10].

To overcome the negative characteristics inherent to conductive polymers, such as insolubility, processing difficulties, and instability under environmental influence, the chemical modification of polyvinylimidazole under the action of 2-amino-5-bromo-1,3,4-thiadiazole was carried out, with the aim of obtaining its derivative with improved electrical conductivity.

Materials and Methods

1-vinylimidazole (Alfa Aesar), 2-amino-5-bromo-1,3,4-thiadiazole (98%, Alfa Aesar)

For the synthesis of this compound, 9.624 mL (0.106 mol) of 1-vinylimidazole monomer and 100 mg (0.61 mmol) of AIBN were dissolved in 96 mL of benzene in a 250 mL three-neck flask and stirred at 60 °C for 24 hours [4,5]. Radical polymerization was carried out under a nitrogen atmosphere. After polymerization, the product was precipitated with acetone. The resulting precipitate was then washed three times with hexane. The obtained PVIm was dried in a vacuum oven at 40 °C for 48 hours, yielding a light yellow powder.

Figure 1. Synthesis process of PVIm-Tia-NH₂ comp from N-vinylimidazole

PVIm (60 mg) and 2-amino-5-bromo-1,3,4-thiadiazole (20 mg) were dissolved in 8 mL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The reaction mixture was incubated at 40 °C for 2 days, after which the unreacted 2-amino-5-bromo-1,3,4-thiadiazole was removed by dialysis in distilled water using a Spectra/Por 7 membrane (molecular weight cutoff = 103). A certain amount of activated cellulose acetate was added to the obtained PVIm-Tia-NH₂ polymer, and the mixture was dried by cooling for 48 hours [6–8].

Furthermore, infrared spectroscopy was employed to confirm the structure of the synthesized PVIm-Tia-NH₂ (Figure 2). Both molecules contain an imidazole ring, and the corresponding vibrations appeared in the PVIm IR spectrum at 1500.34 cm⁻¹, 1418.38 cm⁻¹, 1286.28 cm⁻¹, and 1230.36 cm⁻¹. In the PVIm-Tia-NH₂ composite, the absorption bands associated with the imidazole ring were observed at 1496.49 cm⁻¹, 1418.38 cm⁻¹, 1285.32 cm⁻¹, and 1229.39 cm⁻¹, which are essentially identical to those of PVIm.

The stretching vibration of the azole group in PVIm was observed at 1086.69 cm⁻¹, whereas in the PVIm-Tia-NH₂ composite, the maximum absorption of the azole group was recorded at 1088.6 cm⁻¹. Peaks at 918.91 cm⁻¹, 826.34 cm⁻¹, and 747.28 cm⁻¹ correspond to heterocyclic vibrations in PVIm, while the peaks at 921.80 cm⁻¹, 830.20 cm⁻¹, and 749.20 cm⁻¹ correspond to those in the PVIm-Tia-NH₂ composite.

Notably, absorption bands that were absent in the PVIm spectrum but appeared in the PVIm-Tia-NH₂ spectrum—at 1567.7 cm⁻¹ (N–H), 994.8 cm⁻¹ (C–N), as well as 647.8 cm⁻¹ and

621.12 cm^{-1} (C-S)—confirm that the reaction took place and that PVIm was successfully converted into PVIm-Tia-NH₂.

To investigate the structure of the synthesized polymers, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed.

Figure 2. IR spectrum of PVIm (top) and PVIm-Tia-NH₂ compd (bottom)

Fig. 3. Structural morphology of PVIm (a, b) and PVIm-Tia-NH₂ komp (e, f)

As shown in Figures 3(a,b), PVIm exhibits a granular, powder-like morphology, whereas the PVIm-Tia-NH₂ composite (Figures 3(e,f)) appears in a film-like form.

It is well known that one of the most widely used methods for characterizing the current conduction and other electrical properties of semiconductor materials, diodes, thyristors, and

similar devices is the determination of their current–voltage (I–V) characteristics [11,12]. The I–V characteristic of a conductor is a graphical representation of the relationship between the current passing through the material (with a certain resistance) and the applied voltage.

The current–voltage characteristics (I–V curves) of the PVIm and PVIm-Tia-NH₂ composite materials, both in the dark and under UV illumination ($h\nu = 5.0$ eV), were found to be linear, as shown in Figure 4. These results indicate the potential use of these materials as elements operating in the UV range.

Figure 4. VAC of (a) PVIm and (b) PVIm-Tia-NH₂ comp polymers under saturated in UVL (red) and in the dark (black) $T=300$ K

Conclusion

As can be seen from the above results, the current strength increases linearly with increasing voltage of PVIm and PVIm-tia-NH₂ comp in the dark and when saturated with ultraviolet light. This pattern can be described by Ohm's law. Also, it was observed that when PVIm provides a voltage of 0-100 V in dark conditions, the current strength increases sharply to 38-529 nA. In contrast, when saturated with ultraviolet light, when the voltage was increased to 0-100 V, it was observed that the current increased sharply to 84-813 nA. The same situation was observed in PVIm-tia-NH₂ comp, i.e., when applying a voltage of 0-100 V in dark conditions, the current strength increased sharply to 0,165-1,61 μ A. In contrast, it was observed that when the voltage was increased to 0-100 V when saturated with ultraviolet light, the current increased sharply to 0,63-3,6 μ A. It is worth noting that in both cases (in the dark and when saturated with ultraviolet light), the current strength in PVIm-tia-NH₂ comp ($I=\mu$ A) increases by one unit compared to PVIm($I=n$ A) [13]. The sharp increase in the result when saturated with ultraviolet light compared to the result obtained in the dark can be explained by the internal photoeffect phenomenon.

REFERENCES

1. J. Thunberg, T. Kalogeropoulos *et al.* *In situ* Synthesis of conductive polypyrrole in electrospun cellulose nanofibers: scaffold for neutral tissue engineering. *Cellulose*, 2015, Vol. 22, pp. 1459–1467.
2. Ruiqao Xu *et al.* Highly conductive, twistable and bendable polypyrrole-carbon nanotube fiber for efficient supercapacitor electrodes // *RSC Adv.*, 2015, Vol. 5, pp. 22015–22021.

3. D. Gopakumar *et al.* Flexible papers derived from polypyrrole deposited cellulose nanofibers for enhanced electromagnetic interference shielding in gigahertz frequencies // *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 2021, Vol. 138, No. 16, pp. 1-11.
4. S. Katsuhiko, *et al.* Electrochemical Quantitative Evaluation of the Surface Charge of a Poly(1-Vinylimidazole) Multilayer Film and Application to Nanopore pH Sensor // *Electroanalysis*, 2021, vol. 33; No. 6, p. 1633 – 1638.
5. H. Pan, *et al.* Nitrogen-doped porous carbon with interconnected tubular structure for supercapacitors operating at sub-ambient temperatures // *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 2020, Vol. 401, p. 126083.
6. N. Alexandrina, T., Rodica. Poly(1-vinylimidazole) grafted on magnetic nanoparticles - attainment of novel nanostructures // *Revue Roumaine de Chimie*, 2020, vol. 65; No. 6, p. 611 – 616.
7. Tat'yana, V. Vernitskaya, and Oleg N. Efimov. Polypyrrole: a conducting polymer; its synthesis, properties and applications // *Russian Chemical Reviews*, 1997, Vol. 66, No. 5, pp. 443-457.
8. Yussuf, Abdirahman, *et al.* Synthesis and characterization of conductive polypyrrole: the influence of the oxidants and monomer on the electrical, thermal, and morphological properties. *International Journal of Polymer Science*, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/4191747>.
9. D. Müller *et al.* Chemical in situ polymerization of polypyrrole on bacterial cellulose nanofibers // *Synthetic Metals*, 2011, Vol. 161, pp. 106–111.
10. R. Elashnikov, S. Rimpelová, L. Děkanovský, V. Švorčík. O. Lyutakov. Polypyrrole-coated cellulose nanofibers: influence of orientation, coverage and electrical stimulation on SH-SY5Y behavior // *J. Mater. Chem. B*, 2019, Vol. 7, pp. 6500-6507.
11. Kuo CT, Chiou WH. Field-effect transistor with polyaniline thin film as semiconductor. *Synth Met.* 1997; 88: 2330. doi: 10.1016/S0379-6779(97)80879-X.
12. Tang H, Kumar P, Zhang S, Yi Z, de Crescenzo G, Santato C, *et al.* Conducting polymer transistors making use of activated carbon gate electrodes. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*. 2015;7: 969-973. doi: 10.1021/am507708c.
13. Sardorbek Otajonov, Khamdam Akbarov, Nuritdin Kattaev, Elyor Berdimurodov Abdugafur Mamadalimov, Shokhzod Norbekov , Yong Ill-Lee synthesis, electrophysical, and optical properties of conductive polymers based on poly(1-n-vinylimidazole) 2025, No. 4, pp. 31-40 DOI: 10.32434/0321-4095-2025-161-4-31-40